

CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH THAT DOES NOT INVOLVE THE PROCESSING OF MY PERSONAL DATA

[Research Workshop- Data Collection Date]

I understand that participation in the study is voluntary and that I can stop participating at any time. There will be no negative consequences for me if I withdraw from the study.

I have received information with sufficient information about the study and the processing of the data collected about me so that no personal data about me will be collected, including indirect identifiers that could identify me.

I declare that I have understood the information I have received and wish to participate in the study.

Signature

Date

Note: This consent form has been redacted to remove identifying information (e.g., institutional details, specific event names/dates, contact information) to ensure anonymity for the review process and public sharing as supplementary material. For information on other supplementary materials related to this study that are available, please refer to the Data Availability Statement in the published paper.